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SIMULATION OF INTERLAMINAR DAMAGE USING DECOHESION ELEMENTS

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SUMMARY: An 8-node decohesion element is proposed to simulate delamination onset and growth under single-mode or mixed-mode loading in composite laminates. The element is placed at the interface between solid finite elements representing individual plies or a group of plies. A damage parameter is used in a strain softening law to track the damage state of the interface. The method can be used in conjunction with conventional material degradation procedures to account for both in-plane and interlaminar damage modes and do not require the pre-existence of cracks or self-similarity assumptions for crack growth. The accuracy of the predictions is evaluated in single mode delamination tests, in the mixed-mode bending test, and by comparing numerical predictions with experimental data for a DCB test of a $(0^\circ)_{24}$ CFRP laminate. Good agreement between numerical predictions and experimental results is obtained.

KEYWORDS : Composite Laminates, Delamination, Decohesion Elements.

INTRODUCTION

The fracture process of high performance composite laminates is quite complex, involving both intralaminar damage mechanisms (e.g. matrix cracking, fibre fracture) and interlaminar damage (delamination) (Figure 1). Although some progress has been made lately in the development of accurate tools for the prediction of intralaminar damage growth, similar tools for delamination are still difficult to implement, and thus delamination is generally not considered. Without delamination, the predictive capabilities of progressive failure analyses will remain limited.

Fig. 1- Interaction between intralaminar and interlaminar damage mechanisms [1].

The analysis of delamination is commonly divided into the study of the initiation and the analysis of the propagation of an already initiated area. Delamination initiation analyses are

usually based on stresses and use criteria such as the quadratic interaction of the interlaminar stresses in conjunction with a characteristic distance [2], [3]. This distance is a function of geometry and material properties, so its determination always requires extensive mechanical testing.

Most analyses of delamination growth apply a fracture mechanics approach, such as the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) proposed by Rybicki and Kanninen [4]. Although providing valuable information concerning onset and stability of delamination, the use of VCCT to simulate delamination growth requires complex moving mesh techniques and advancing the crack front when the local energy release rates rise to critical values. Furthermore, an initial crack must be defined and, for certain geometries and load cases, the location of the delamination front might not be obvious.

One approach to overcome the above limitations of the VCCT is the use of interfacial decohesion elements placed between the composite layers. This approach is based on a Dugdale-Barenblatt type cohesive zone [5], and was first applied to the analysis of concrete cracking by Hillerborg *et al.* [6]. The proposed constitutive equations for the interface are phenomenological mechanical relations between the tractions and interfacial separations. The work of normal and tangential separation can be related to the critical values of energy release rates.

In order to predict delamination onset and growth, an 8-node decohesion element is developed and implemented in the ABAQUS finite element code [7] using a user-subroutine UEL. The element is used to model the interface between sublaminates. A bi-linear strain softening constitutive equation is implemented such that the element does not carry any tensile or shear loads after the interfacial fracture energy has been consumed.

DECOHESION ELEMENT FORMULATION

In order to predict the onset and growth of delamination, the 8-node plane decohesion element shown in Figure 2 was developed and implemented in the ABAQUS finite element code [7]. The element consists of a zero-thickness volumetric element in which the interpolating shape functions for the top and bottom faces are compatible with the kinematics of the elements that are being connected to it. The material response built into the element represents damage using a cohesive zone ahead of crack tip.

Fig. 2- Eight-node decohesion element, $t = 0$ [8].

Element kinematics

The formulation of plane decohesion elements requires the definition of the relative displacements between the top and bottom surfaces of the element. These displacements are obtained using the standard isoparametric linear Lagrangian shape functions:

$$\mathbf{u}_{\text{top}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_x \\ \mathbf{u}_y \\ \mathbf{u}_z \end{Bmatrix}_{\text{top}} = \mathbf{N}\mathbf{u}_{\text{top}}^e \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\text{bottom}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_x \\ \mathbf{u}_y \\ \mathbf{u}_z \end{Bmatrix}_{\text{bottom}} = \mathbf{N}\mathbf{u}_{\text{bottom}}^e \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{N} is the matrix of shape functions and $\mathbf{u}_{\text{top}}^e$ and $\mathbf{u}_{\text{bottom}}^e$ are the vectors of nodal displacements of the top and bottom surfaces of the element respectively. The displacements in local co-ordinates can be obtained as:

$$\mathbf{u}_{\text{top,bottom}}^{\text{local}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{u}_t \\ \mathbf{u}_n \end{Bmatrix}_{\text{top,bottom}} = \hat{\mathbf{e}}^T \mathbf{u}_{\text{top,bottom}} \quad (3)$$

Where the transformation matrix \mathbf{q} is defined by the unit vectors corresponding to the local directions (n: normal, s and t: tangential) as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}} = [\hat{\mathbf{v}}_s \quad \hat{\mathbf{v}}_t \quad \hat{\mathbf{v}}_n] \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_s = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{v}}_\xi}{\|\hat{\mathbf{v}}_\xi\|}; \hat{\mathbf{v}}_n = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{v}}_\xi \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_\eta}{\|\hat{\mathbf{v}}_\xi \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_\eta\|}; \hat{\mathbf{v}}_t = \hat{\mathbf{v}}_n \times \hat{\mathbf{v}}_s \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_\xi = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{\partial z}{\partial \xi} \end{Bmatrix}; \hat{\mathbf{v}}_\eta = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta} \\ \frac{\partial z}{\partial \eta} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The local relative displacements between the bottom and top surfaces required to define the element constitutive equation can now be obtained as:

$$\mathbf{\ddot{a}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{u}_t \\ \mathbf{u}_n \end{Bmatrix}_{\text{top}} - \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_s \\ \mathbf{u}_t \\ \mathbf{u}_n \end{Bmatrix}_{\text{bottom}} = \hat{\mathbf{e}}^T \mathbf{N}\mathbf{u}_{\text{top}}^e - \hat{\mathbf{e}}^T \mathbf{N}\mathbf{u}_{\text{bottom}}^e = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}^e \quad (7)$$

With:

$$\mathbf{B} = \hat{\mathbf{e}}^T [\mathbf{N} \quad -\mathbf{N}] \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^e = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{\text{top}}^e \\ \mathbf{u}_{\text{bottom}}^e \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Element constitutive equation

An appropriate constitutive equation in the formulation of the interface element is fundamental for an accurate simulation of the fracture process. A constitutive equation is used to relate the stress σ to the relative displacement δ at the interface. Some strain softening models that have been proposed include: linear elastic-perfectly plastic; linear elastic-linear softening; linear elastic-progressive softening; linear elastic-regressive softening [8]. One characteristic of all softening models is that the cohesive zone can still transfer load after the onset of damage. For pure Mode I, II or III loading, after the interfacial normal or shear stresses attain their respective interlaminar tensile or shear strengths, the stiffnesses are gradually reduced to zero. The area under the stress-relative displacement curves is the respective (Mode I, II or III) fracture toughness. Using the J integral proposed by Rice [9], it can be shown that for small cohesive zones:

$$\int_0^{\delta^F} \sigma(\delta) d\delta = G_c \quad (10)$$

Where G_c is the critical energy release rate for a particular mode, and δ^F is the corresponding relative displacement at failure. The bi-linear constitutive equation shown in Figure 3 (for single mode loading) is adopted in the current work.

Fig. 3- Bi-linear constitutive equations [8].

Before damage onset, point 1 in Figure 3, there is a high stiffness (penalty stiffness) that holds the top and bottom layers together. When the applied stress is equal to the corresponding allowable, point 2, the softening process is initiated. It is considered that a softening point unloads towards the origin (point 3). The energy consumed in the fracture process for a softening point (point 3) is given by the area of the triangle 0-2-3. The critical value of the energy release rate is attained at point 4. For any relative displacement larger than point 4, complete decohesion occurs and the interface does not carry any tensile or shear loads (point 5). If the load is reversed, interpenetration is avoided by reapplying the penalty stiffness.

The bilinear interfacial constitutive response shown in Figure 3 can be implemented as follows:

- i) $\delta < \delta^0 \Rightarrow$ the constitutive equation is given by:

$$\sigma = K_p \delta \quad (11)$$

- ii) $\delta^0 \leq \delta < \delta^F \Rightarrow$ the constitutive equation is given by:

$$\sigma = (1 - D)K_p \delta \quad (12)$$

Where D represents the damage accumulated at the interface, which is zero initially, and reaches 1 when the material is fully damaged.

- iii) $\delta \geq \delta^F \Rightarrow$ all the penalty stiffnesses are set equal to zero. If crack closure is detected,

interpenetration is prevented by reapplying only the normal stiffness. Frictional effects are neglected.

The properties required to define the bilinear interfacial softening behavior are the penalty stiffness K_p , the fracture energies and the corresponding nominal interlaminar strengths. It should be noted that the accuracy of the analysis depends on the penalty stiffness K_p that is chosen. High values of K_p avoid interpenetration of the crack faces but can lead to numerical problems. Following previous analyses [10] a penalty stiffness of 10^6 N/mm^3 was used. This value avoids potential convergence problems during the nonlinear procedure.

The previously described formulation is valid for single-mode loading. Softening onset is defined by a strength allowable and complete decohesion by the respective fracture toughness. However, under mixed-mode loading, softening onset might start before any of the stresses reaches the respective allowable and complete decohesion might occur before any of the energy release rates reach the respective critical value. This means that failure criteria taking into account interactions between stress components and mixed-mode energy release rates are required.

The approach proposed by Dávila *et al.* [8] is used in the current work. The criterion used to predict softening onset is:

$$\sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_z}{T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{xz}}{S}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{yz}}{S}\right)^2} = 1 \quad (13)$$

where σ_z is the transverse normal tensile stress and τ_{xz} and τ_{yz} are the transverse shear stresses. T and S are the nominal normal tensile and shear strengths, respectively. Total interfacial decohesion occurs if the following criterion is satisfied:

$$\sqrt{\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}}\right)^2} = 1 \quad (14)$$

The three-dimensional form of (11)-(12) can be expressed as:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{D})\mathbf{C}\dot{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix, \mathbf{C} is the undamaged constitutive matrix:

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} K_p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_p \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

and \mathbf{D} is a diagonal matrix representing the damage accumulated at the interface:

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} d & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & d & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

The term d on the diagonal is the damage parameter, which is a non-linear function of δ_m^{\max} , the highest mixed-mode relative displacement experienced by the material, and is defined in Ref. [8].

ELEMENT VALIDATION

Three test problems were selected to validate the decohesion element. The first problem consists of the double cantilever beam (DCB) test used to determine Mode I toughness. The second problem modelled consists of the end-notched flexure test (ENF) used for Mode II toughness measurement. The third test is the mixed mode bending test (MMB). All three of these problems have analytical solutions that were previously developed for isotropic adherents [11]. These closed form solutions provide an approximate framework against which to assess the FE formulation. The results obtained using a previously developed 18-node interface element [10] are also presented for all the cases analysed.

DCB test

The ASTM standard specimen used to determine the interlaminar fracture toughness in Mode I (G_{Ic}) is the double-cantilever beam (DCB) specimen shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4- DCB test specimen.

In order to compare the results obtained with the closed-form solutions aluminium adherents were simulated. A 100-mm-long specimen, 10 mm-wide, and composed of two 1.5-mm-thick aluminium adherents was simulated. The initial crack length is 30 mm. The properties of the interface are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Properties of the DCB specimen interface.

G_{Ic}	G_{IIc}	T	S	K_p
0.268 N/mm	1.45 N/mm	30. MPa	40. MPa	10^6 N/mm ³

The ABAQUS finite element model consists of two layers of C3D8I incompatible-mode 8-noded elements. Anticlastic effects were neglected and only one element was used across the width. One hundred elements were used along the span of the model, corresponding to an element length of 1 mm. A plot of reaction force as a function of the applied end displacement is shown in Figure 5. A good agreement between the two solutions is obtained.

Fig. 5- Load-deflection plot for DCB test.

ENF test

The ENF test shown in Figure 6 is often used to determine Mode II fracture toughness. The geometry of the specimen is the same as the one used in the DCB specimen and the same properties for the interface are used.

Fig. 6- ENF test specimen.

The load-deflection responses for the finite element model and the analytical prediction are shown in Figure 7. It can be observed that all solutions are in excellent agreement.

Fig. 7- Load-deflection plot for ENF test.

MMB test

The most widely used specimen for mixed-mode fracture is the mixed-mode bending (MMB) specimen shown in Figure 8, which was proposed by Reeder and Crews [12]. The main advantages of the MMB test method are the possibility of using virtually the same specimen configuration as for Mode I tests and varying the mixed mode ratio from pure Mode I to pure Mode II.

Fig. 8- MMB test specimen.

The specimen analysed here has the same geometry and properties as the DCB and ENF specimens. The length of the MMB lever was chosen as 26.11 mm, which corresponds to a ratio of 5.41 for G_{II}/G_I and to a ratio of 2.916 between the load at the mid-span of the beam and the opening load. Taking into account that $G_{IC}/G_{IC}=5.41$, the same contribution of Mode I and Mode II loading for crack propagation is used.

The load deflection curve calculated from FEM and two beam solutions from [11] are shown in Figure 9. One beam solution assumes a quadratic interaction between the energy release rates, and the other assumes a linear interaction. A mixed-mode failure criterion based on a moving damage surface is used in the 18-node interface element [10]. Reasonably good correlation for the global behaviour is obtained among all three methods. The difference in peak loads can be a result of the delamination propagation before the peak load predicted by the numerical models and of the geometrically non-linear effects considered in the numerical models and not taken into account in the analytical solutions.

Fig. 9- Load-deflection plot for MMB test.

SIMULATION OF A DCB TEST IN A CFRP LAMINATE

A DCB test of a unidirectional CFRP laminate for which experimental information is available [13] is investigated. The model prediction is compared with both closed-form analytical solutions and the experimental data.

A 24-ply unidirectional CFRP specimen containing a thin insert at the mid-plane near the loaded end was simulated. The specimen is 150 mm long, 20 mm wide, and composed of two 1.98-mm-thick plies of unidirectional material. The initial crack length is 55 mm. The properties of the graphite material are shown in Table 2, and the properties of the interface are shown in Table 3.

Table 2- Properties of the CFRP [13].

E_{11}	$E_{22}=E_{33}$	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	$G_{12}=G_{13}$	G_{23}
150. MPa	11. MPa	0.25	0.45	6.0 MPa	3.7 MPa

Table 3- Properties of the DCB specimen interface [13].

G_{Ic}	G_{IIc}	T	S	K_p
0.268 N/mm	1.45 N/mm	30. MPa	40. MPa	10^6 N/mm ³

A plot of reaction force as a function of the applied end displacement is shown in Figure 10. The beam solution was previously developed [11] for isotropic adherent materials and using plane stress assumptions. It is clear that the beam solution is stiffer than the test and FEM results, which is probably due to the assumption of isotropy and to the use of simple beam theory in the analytical solution. After the propagation of delamination, fibre bridging in the test specimen causes a small drift in the response compared to the FEM and analytical solutions.

Fig. 10- Load-deflection response of the CFRP DCB test.

CONCLUSIONS

A method for the simulation of progressive delamination based on decohesion elements is presented. Decohesion elements are placed between layers of solid elements simulating delamination propagation in response to the loading situation. The onset of damage and the growth of delamination can be simulated without previous knowledge about the location, the size, and the direction of propagation of the delaminations. A strain softening law for mixed-mode delamination was used. Four examples were presented that test the accuracy of the method. Models of the DCB and ENF test represent cases of single-mode crack growth, whereas the MMB test represents crack propagation in Mixed-Mode I and II. Good agreement between the numerical and closed-form solutions is obtained. The models using 8-node decohesion element provided similar results to the models with a larger number of degrees of freedom, using 18-node decohesion elements. The comparison between analytical solutions based on simple beam theory of a DCB test in a $(0^\circ)_{24}$ CFRP laminate with experimental data

highlights the overly stiff analytical solution in the linear part of the test. However, an excellent agreement between the numerical and experimental data is obtained.

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